

Milestone: M2.1: Community engagement scoreboard created

Lead Participant: UNIPD

Author: Federica Quaglia (UNIPD), Silvio Tosatto (UNIPD)

Due: 31 July 2024 (M6)

Date Of Completion: 27/06/2024

Means of Verification

[WP2 M2.1: Community Engagement Scoreboard](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Project participants & others

WP Leads: Silvio Tosatto (UNIPD), Fotis Psomopoulos (CERTH), John Hancock (UL)

WP2 members, WP3 members

Next action steps

- Discuss and plan for updates during WP2-WP3 F2F in Padova, 2-3 October 2024
- Update regularly and add efficiency indicators
- Finalize for M2.4: Community engagement scoreboard updated (M24)

ELIXIR-STEERS is funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101131096.

